

TOURIST PERCEPTION TOWARDS SMALL AND MEDIUM SIZED ACCOMMODATIONS IN GOA

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Abstract

Tourism is considered important factor for social, economic, cultural, spiritual and artistic development of the country. Goa has emerged a most favorite destination for both domestic and international tourist. Tourism enterprises plays important role by providing tourism products and services to the tourists. Tourism Enterprises are classified into five main broad categories viz Accommodation, Food and Beverages, Travel and Recreation and Entertainment. The present study focuses on Small and medium sized accommodations. Small and medium accommodation are classified based on Accommodation plays important role in giving home feeling to the tourist. The main aim of this paper is to identify and measure tourist perceptions towards small and medium accommodations in Goa. Data has been collected from 280 tourists including both domestic and international. Collected data was analyzed by using factor analysis and multiple regression analysis was used to measure impact of tourist perception. This study reveals that factors identified has positive impact on tourist perception

Keywords: Tourists, Perception, Accommodation, Impact

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of growing industry in India. Marin (1992), tourism receipts can boost the economic growth of a country through their positive influence on the economy as a whole in recent years study relating to tourism enterprises is growing in India as number of tourism enterprises are growing rapidly. Goa is tiny state in India and has attracted the attention of large number of domestic and foreign tourists. As per data collected from Goa Tourism Development Corporation website, more domestic tourists visits Goa as compared to foreign tourists. Tourism Enterprises are broadly classified into five major categories like Food and Beverages, Accommodations, Travel and Recreation and Entertainment. Small and medium enterprises are classified based on their facilities provided and number of workers employed. Thus, according to Breen (Breen et al., 2005) small and medium tourism enterprises comprise all businesses, which operate in the tourism industry and employ up to hundred employees and include sole operators. Specifically, micro businesses are those that employ between one and four workers, small businesses employ between five and nineteen employees and medium businesses employ between twenty and hundred employees. Tourism business is distributed across five main industry groups: accommodation, transportation, food and beverages services, travel services, travel services and entertainment.

Accommodation services in Goa

Accommodation is establishments that provide a place for the tourist to stay i.e. lodging facilities which are paid for the duration of the stay by the tourist. As per Ahmada (2015) Small and medium sized hotels are defined as those with fewer than 50 rooms and fewer than 10 employees. They are often classified as low end accommodation and are situated in main tourist's location. Accommodation in Goa is plentiful with a variety of hotels, resorts and guest houses to suit every budget and every taste.

Table no: 1 showing number of accommodations in Goa

Hotel types	No. of hotels in North Goa	No. of hotels in South Goa
Category A	21	11
Category B	144	64
Category C	07	209
Category D	1595	436

Source: GTDC website

Review of Literature

Xie (2011), aimed at measuring tourist-perceived quality for three tourist attractions in Xi'an to find out countermeasures for increasing customer revisit and improving tourism management performance. Giritlioglu, Jones et.al (2012) developed an instrument to evaluate food and beverage service quality in spa hotels, identified aspects of food and beverage service quality of which customers had the highest expectations and measured customer perceptions of the spa hotels in this study. Dani (2014) measured customer satisfaction for F&B chains in Pune using American Customer Satisfaction Index Model. Ivana (2014), examines the concept and measurement of quality of service in the hotel sector. Ganapala (2015), discussed the relationship between motivations, attitude and perception to study tourist behaviour and found that tourist are satisfied and are willing to revisit destination. Agarwal (2015) analyzed the nature and set up of Accommodation industry in Dehradun and Mussoorie and even to understand the quality of goods and services being offered to the tourist. Jayewardene (2016) studied service quality levels offered to customers in travel agencies to gain an idea to set efficient measures. Kumar and Bhatnagar (2017), studied effect of food and service quality on customer satisfaction with reference to 3 star hotels in Punjab region. Ramraj (2018), found that domestic tourists has positive, significant and moderate relation for their intention to stay in future. Saravanan (2019), formulated an appropriate service quality questionnaire for measuring service quality in budget category hotels. Uslu(2020) tested the relationship between the service quality of restaurants and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) communication, satisfaction, and behavioural intention analysed the moderating effect of the restaurant atmosphere in the relationship between service quality and eWOM. Velraj (2021), investigated the relationships between services quality, food quality; one of the basic needs of the human being is food. Bayad Ali, Gardi , Othman (2021),reveled the impact of service quality on tourist satisfaction and found that empathy, responsiveness, assurance and tangibles has positive

relation with customer satisfaction and reliability has negative relation with the tourist satisfaction. Jangra, Kaushik et.al (2021), examines perception and attitude towards tourism impact on Chitkul, Kalpa, and Nako in Kinnaur.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To identify the determinants of small and medium sized accommodations in Goa.
2. To measure the tourists' perceived image small and medium sized accommodation in Goa on different determinants identified.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data collection

For the purpose of study data has been collected from primary and secondary source. Primary data has been collected from the 280 tourists including both domestic and foreign. Out of total sample 196 tourists belong to domestic and 84 are foreign tourists. Determinants of small and medium sized accommodations are identified by reviewing literature of various researchers in the field of tourism enterprises. The identified factors are then tested for relevance tourism enterprises study specific to Goa. The factor analysis, reduced the determinants of small and medium sized accommodation into a smaller number, which were further analyzed using multiple linear regression to study the extend of influence on tourist's perception.

Unit of Analysis

For the study unit of analysis is number of tourists who visit Goa for leisure. Tourists are broadly classified into domestic and foreign. Foreign tourists surveyed belonged to different nationalities viz. British, German and Russian tourists whereas domestic tourists belongs to Indian nationalities from different states.

Sampling Procedure

A random sampling technique was used to collect information from foreign and domestic tourists. 280 tourists were interviewed from North and south Goa. The sample size was restricted due to short data collection period. Data was collected during peak season i.e from November to January.

Survey Instrument

Structured questionnaire was used to collect data by using 7 point Likert scale. The first section of questionnaire includes demographic profile of the respondent viz. age, gender, education level, income level etc. and second section includes factors affecting tourist perception towards services of small and medium sized accommodations

Graph no1: Showing percentage of Tourists arrival statistics

Source: GTDC website

The above graph shows that domestic tourist visited Goa from 2015 to 2020 is more as compared to the foreign tourists

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Tourist Perception towards select small and medium tourism enterprises in Goa

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The sample of tourists surveyed include 70 % i.e. 196 tourists are domestic tourists and 30% i.e.84 are foreign tourists. Tourist surveyed included, 52% female respondents and 48% male respondents. The vast majority of the sample which is, 89% belonged to the age category of 26-50,8% belonged to the age category of 18-25 and the balance 3% belonged to the age category of 50 and above. 66% of the sample said they were married and the balance were not married. In terms of occupation, 47% of the sample was represented by domestic tourists who were in service either private or with the government, 18% were self-employed, 23% were homemakers and the balance 12% were retired. In terms of income, the vast majority of the domestic tourists i.e. (89%) belonged to the annual income category of Rs.250000 and Rs.1000000, which represents a strong tilt towards middle to upper middle-income groups. In terms of foreign tourists majority of the tourist's income is more. 11% of the respondents were visiting Goa alone or with friends and 89% with family. An over whelming majority looked at Goa as a short weekend holiday destination with a huge 84% having a stay for less than 1 week. 64% of the samples were tourists who had visited the state in the past and the balance 36% were visiting it for the first time.

Table no: 2 showing Tourists rating to the identified determinants of Accommodations in Goa

Sr. no	Determinants/Factors	N	Mean
1	Immediate responsiveness to customer request	280	6.1286
2	Beds are cleaned and arranged with washed blankets	280	5.7393
3	Prompt service of staff	280	5.7250
4	Neat & professional appearance of front office staff	280	5.4000
5	Technically equipped with television, phone, and internet connection in rooms.	280	5.0536
6	Neatly decorated and highly facilitated rooms	280	4.9714
7	Pleasant atmosphere	280	4.9071
8	Clean and comfortable rooms	280	4.8893
9	Rooms with A./c, Refrigerators , lighting	280	4.7464
10	Basic amenities in the rooms.	280	4.7393
11	Appealing interior and exterior décor	280	4.5179
12	Professional and experienced staff with good communication skill	280	4.5179
13	Easy accessible of restaurant, pub and bar	280	4.5500
14	Neatly maintained garden	280	4.5393
15	Safety and security	280	4.1929
16	Transportation facilities till restaurant.	280	4.0000
17	Sufficient parking provision	280	4.0000
18	Hygienic bathrooms and toilets	280	3.2464
19	Spacious rooms	280	2.9643
20	Convenient hotel location	280	2.8571

The identification of 20 determinants of accommodation helped to achieve first objective of the study. These identified determinants are basis to achieve second objective of the research i.e. measure the tourists' perceived image small and medium sized accommodation in Goa

Table no: 3 showing KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser – Meyer –Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.878
	Approx. Chi-square	12054.202
Bartlett Test of Sphericity	Df.	528
	Sig.	0

Analysis using Principal Component Analysis

The Principal component factor analysis was used to analyze the collected data. The result of Kaiser – Meyer –Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy is 0.878, which is higher than 0.5, the result was significant ($p < 0.001$), as suggested by, Hair et al (2010), For the study total variance explained is 82.924. The total 25 determinants are reduced to 4 factors 1) Room service 2) Staff service 3) Ambience and maintenance 4) Other Services . Screen plot shown in fig 1 depict the formation of this factors.

The factors clubbed into Room Service includes clean and comfortable rooms, basic amenities in the rooms, neatly decorated and highly facilitated rooms, rooms with A./c, refrigerators ,lighting technically equipped with television, phone, and internet connection in rooms. The factors clubbed into staff service includes neat & professional appearance of front office staff, prompt service of staff, immediate responsiveness to customer request, professional and experienced staff with good communication skill. The ambience and repairs and maintenance includes convenient hotel location, hygienic bathrooms and toilets, appealing interior and exterior decor, neatly maintained garden , hygienic bathrooms and toilets, pleasant atmosphere, spacious rooms easy accessible of restaurant, pub and bar. Provision for parking, transportation facilities till restaurant and safety and security are included in other services provided by hotel. The first factor Room service explains 29.268% % total variance, second factor Staff service explains 27.385 % of total variance, third factor Ambience and repair and maintenance 20.047% total variance and fourth factor explains Other services explains 16.473% of total variance as shown in table no.4.

Table no: 4 Total Variance Explained

Component	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.854	29.268	29.268
2	5.477	27.385	56.653
3	4.009	20.047	76.700
4	3.295	16.473	93.173
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			

Table no 5: Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
A1	1.000	.838
A2	1.000	.913
A3	1.000	.901
A4	1.000	.857
A5	1.000	.862
A6	1.000	.911
A7	1.000	.896
A8	1.000	.822
A9	1.000	.819
A10	1.000	.706
A11	1.000	.757
A12	1.000	.850
A13	1.000	.936
A14	1.000	.886
A15	1.000	.800
A16	1.000	.769
A17	1.000	.902
A18	1.000	.917
A19	1.000	.856
A20	1.000	.740

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Communalities for all the variables range from .706 to .917

Screen Plot (Factor Analysis)

Fig. 1. Screen Plot

Table no: 6 showing pattern matrix

Factors / Determinants	1	2	3	4
Technically equipped with television, phone, and internet connection in rooms.	.957			
Rooms with A./c, Refrigerators , lighting	.950			
Beds are cleaned and arranged with washed blankets	.940			
Basic amenities in the rooms	.936			
Clean and comfortable rooms	.894			
Neatly decorated and highly facilitated rooms	.888			
Hygienic bathrooms and toilets		.962		
Convenient hotel location		.948		
Pleasant atmosphere		.936		
Neatly maintained garden		.801		
Spacious rooms		.760		
Easy accessible of restaurant, pub and bar		.694		
Appealing interior and exterior décor		.693		
Immediate responsiveness to customer request			.921	

Professional and experienced staff with good communication skill			.917	
Prompt service of staff			.824	
Neat & professional appearance of front office staff			.733	
Transportation facilities till restaurant.				.896
Sufficient parking provision				.896
Safety and Security				.782

Analysis using multiple regression analysis

The four factors (Room service, Staff service , Ambience and maintenance and Other services) identified by using Principal Component Analysis is further analyzed using multiple regression analysis to study the impact of identified factors on tourists perception towards services of small and medium sized accommodations in Goa. For the regression, image ratings given by tourists is taken as dependent variable and five factors identified by the tourists is taken as independent variable.

Table no 7: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.079	.000		.000	1.000
Staff Service	.200	.000	.220	7.12	.000
Room Service	.300	.000	.460	1.46	.000
Ambience and Maintenance	.350	.000	.501	1.70	.000
Other Service	.150	.000	.210	5.5	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Average Ratings of Tourist

All the identified factors; Room service, Staff service, Ambience and Repairs and Maintenance and Other services a were found to be statistically significant contributors to the perceived destination image of Goa from the perception of tourists visiting Goa. As can be seen from their β values, all 4 factors are positively affecting the perceived small and medium sized hotels in Goa. Ambience and Repairs and Maintenance, causes the maximum variance to destination image ($\beta = .501$). Factors; Room service staff services has β value of 0.460 and 0.220 respectively. Other services, as a factor has the 4th highest level of variance with β value of 0.210. (Refer table no.7)

CONCLUSION

Goa is one of the lively tourist's destinations. It is famous for places of historic monuments and beaches. The study revealed that domestic tourists who visit Goa are more as compared to foreign tourists, and most of them are financially well. Majority of them visit Goa for less than

two weeks. In this study only small and medium tourism accommodations are considered. Small and medium enterprises are classified depending upon number of rooms and number of employees in hotel. Hotels having less than 50 rooms and 10 employees are classified as small and medium sized hotels. For the purpose of study twenty factors influencing tourist perception viz. Technically equipped with television, phone, and internet connection in room, Rooms with A/c, Refrigerators, lighting, Beds are cleaned and arranged with washed blankets, Basic amenities in the rooms, Clean and comfortable rooms, Neatly decorated and highly facilitated rooms, Hygienic bathrooms and toilets, Convenient hotel location, Pleasant atmosphere, Neatly maintained garden, Spacious rooms, Easy accessible of restaurant, pub and bar, Appealing interior and exterior décor, Immediate responsiveness to customer request, Professional and experienced staff with good communication skill, Prompt service of staff, Neat & professional appearance of front office staff, Transportation facilities till restaurant, Sufficient parking provision, Safety and Security were considered. These factors were further reduced to four major factors viz. Room Service, Staff Service, Amenities and maintenance and Other Services. Ambience and repairs has maximum variance followed by other factors. All factors have positive impact on tourist satisfaction.

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